

Policy Brief 4: Recommendations

The Planning of Arctic Landscapes and Seascapes and Its Impact on Sustainability

Across the Arctic, there is a surge of new economic activities, ranging from energy development to new transportation systems, from resource exploitation to tourism. Significantly impacting landscapes, livelihoods, and ways of lives, new economic activities in many cases give rise to competing uses of spaces.

Landscape planning—as the field dealing with the development of the physical environment—therefore often finds itself grappling with fundamental questions of justice. Which stakeholders have privileged access to specific landscapes and seascapes? Which actors should have that access?

Because the effects of landscape planning are long-term, they bear not only on circumstances here and now but on future generations as well. At its core, landscape planning implicates the question of distributive justice, the fair distribution of burdens and benefits within a community and across generations.

Examining spatial planning in new economic activities related to tourism, transport, and resources exploitation in the Arctic, the research has analyzed the extent to which existing regulatory frameworks and decision-making processes are geared toward promoting justice for the range of stakeholders involved.

Going forward, this brief points to several steps that can be taken to address such situations:

- 1 In the case of competing uses of landscapes and seascapes, it is imperative to find ways for indigenous communities to benefit from the physical environment in other ways than through traditional livelihoods in order to enhance justice in spatial planning**
- 2 Decision-making processes should be limited in time and offer local communities sufficient time to engage with it and, if need be, to reorganize their ways of living and livelihoods in accordance with the outcome, so as to minimize potential negative consequences**
- 3 Properly acknowledging the range of competing spatial uses, claims and benefits of a given process is a necessary condition for strengthening the participation of all involved stakeholders—and thus for enhancing distributive justice**

